

Selective Excitation of Circular Helical Modes in Graded Index Fibers

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Abstract : The impact of selective excitation of circular helical modes of graded-index fibers on its capacity is analyzed using a model for propagation delay variation with launch offset and angle that resulted from misalignment of source and fiber axis. Results show that promising technique to improve graded-index fiber capacities.

Keywords : fiber measurements, fiber optic, communications, circular helical modes

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